

APPENDIX B

Conversation structures by CPS skill

The following diagrams correspond to structures of a generic conversations around each of the collaborative problem solving skills

Dialog structure A1

CPS Skill: Discovering perspectives and abilities of team members

Figure B.1: Conversation structure to assess A1 skill

Dialog structure A2

CPS Skill: Discovering the type of collaborative interaction to solve the problem, along with goals

Figure B.2: Conversation structure to assess A2 skill

Dialog structure A3
CPS Skill: Understanding roles to solve problem

Figure B.3: Conversation structure to assess A3 skill

Dialog structure B1
CPS Skill: Building a shared representation and negotiating the meaning of the problem
(common ground)

Figure B.4: Conversation structure to assess B1 skill

Dialog structure B2

CPS Skill: Identifying and describing tasks to be completed

Figure B.5: Conversation structure to assess B2 skill

Dialog structure B3

CPS Skill: Describe roles and team organization (communication protocol/rules of engagement)

Figure B.6: Conversation structure to assess B3 skill

Dialog structure C1

CPS Skill: Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed

Figure B.7: Conversation structure to assess C1 skill

Dialog structure C2

CPS Skill: Enacting plans

This skill was related to actions that test takers took to solve the problem. As a result, no dialog structure is created.

Dialog structure C3

CPS Skill: Following rules of engagement, (e.g., prompting other team members to perform their tasks.)

Figure B.8: Conversation structure to assess C3 skill

Dialog structure D1
 CPS Skill: Monitoring and repairing the shared understanding

Figure B.9: Conversation structure to assess D1 skill

Dialog structure D2
 CPS Skill: Monitoring results of actions and evaluating success in solving the problem

Figure B.10: Conversation structure to assess D2 skill

Dialog structure D3

CPS Skill: Monitoring, providing feedback and adapting the team organisation and roles

Figure B.11: Conversation structure to assess D3 skill